

Towards a nature-positive economy roadmap for Europe

PUBLIC CONSULTATION

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Help us build a Nature-Positive Economy Roadmap for Europe – Public Consultation

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1. Introduction

This report presents the results of a synthesis exercise, designed to provide a targeted capture of current initiatives and activities in Europe and beyond that are enabling a transition towards the nature-positive economy (NPE).

This work consolidates an evidence base that provides an indicative baseline of ‘where we are today’ and where leading organizations and countries are advocating for ‘future priorities’ and ‘pathways to transformation’.

This work will be combined with parallel efforts to develop multi-stakeholder NPE roadmaps in our pilot sectors to inform the development of an overall high-level GoNaturePositive! NPE Roadmap for Europe to be launched in 2027.

1. Introduction

The current NPE landscape is fast moving yet the scale of the challenge remains immense. Where ambitious economic policies and strategies do exist, there is ongoing uncertainty around implementation and whether targets will be achieved. Trends also include regulatory roll-backs, delays, and simplification efforts.

Given the inherent complexity, nature and biodiversity often lacks the private-sector uptake versus other competing and more easily measurable sustainability priorities.

We present a range of statistical data, future ambitions and current/planned initiatives. We invite you to help us take stock of this complex picture and share your own conclusions and suggestions to inform the development of our NPE roadmap for Europe.

2. Approach

Reviewing policy and economic data

Investigated and identified core and associated cross-sector European policies that are aligned to the Nature Positive Economy. Extracted relevant economic data from the publicly available Eurostat database.

Review of existing NPE roadmaps

Examined eight recently launched Nature Positive Economy Roadmaps seeking to advance agendas at national level (Austria, UK, Japan and Australia), for business and finance (EU), and expert bodies working across all stakeholder groups (Global).

Targeted review of literature

Drawing on c.110 references to literature from academia and practice, an assessment was conducted to shortlist the promising market opportunities, leading to 10 key clusters of high future potential. Also, around 29 sources were consulted to extract baseline assessments and challenges, cutting across policy and regulation, finance and investment, technology, and societal change.

Key Findings

Where are we now?

KEY FINDINGS 1 – Quantifying the Nature Positive Economy in Europe

ECONOMIC DATA

Key Findings 1 presents some quantitative indications of current efforts in Europe (not exhaustive) to simultaneously tackle both (a) reducing nature-negative economic activities (avoid, minimise, restore and offset) and (b) accelerating nature-positive economic activities (protection, regeneration), leading to a transformation of our socio-economic systems, and contributing towards the full recovery of nature by 2050 and prosperity for all.

We welcome suggestions to include other comparable quantitative datasets from reputable sources in our analysis going forward.

Lastly, although we focus on economic data, we recognise that nature holds many different, equally important types of worth (like spiritual, cultural, intrinsic).

INTERPRETATION & CAVEATS

- I) Under-measurement: existing economic metrics and data rarely incorporates the true value of nature and its services
- II) Valuation methods: there are no simple measures like carbon, rather biodiversity and nature measures are diverse and must be adaptable to uncertainty
- III) Vested interests: different regions in Europe will gain more or less depending on existing (or potential future) natural capital (landscapes, water, ocean) and environmental conditions/variables (heat, wind, etc.)
- IV) Data accuracy: cited stats may be based on limited data and uncertain assumptions

National expenditure on environmental protection by institutional sector in the EU-27

in € Mio. measured in current prices

DATA EXPLANATION

Data is based on mandatory reporting, which covers the following characteristics which are defined in accordance with European Systems of Accounts (ESA):

- output of environmental protection services. Market output, non-market output and output of ancillary activities are distinguished,
- intermediate consumption of environmental protection services,
- intermediate consumption of environmental protection services for production of environmental protection services,
- imports and exports of environmental protection services,
- valued added tax (VAT) and other taxes less subsidies on products on environmental protection services,
- gross fixed capital formation and acquisitions less disposals of non-financial non-produced assets for the production of environmental protection services,
- final consumption of environmental protection services,
- environmental protection transfers (received/paid).

Source:
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/env_ac_ep_ea_sims.htm

Note: Data measured at current prices and not adjusted for inflation.

Source: Eurostat (2025). National expenditure on environmental protection by institutional sector. DOI: https://doi.org/10.2908/ENV_AC_EPNEIS1 (latest access on 11/20/2025)

Employment in the EGSS in the EU-27

Percentage in EGSS to total employment

The Environmental Goods and Services Sector (EGSS) includes activities classified as environmental protection (CEPA) and resource management (CReMA).

Environmental protection activities prevent, reduce, or eliminate pollution and environmental degradation, including the restoration of habitats and ecosystems. Examples include electric vehicles, emission filters, wastewater treatment systems, and noise insulation.

Resource management activities aim to preserve natural resources and prevent their depletion. Examples include renewable energy production, energy-efficient buildings, seawater desalination, and rainwater harvesting.

Some CEPA and CReMA products and activities are more closely linked to the protection and sustainable management of nature and biodiversity than others. However, due to data limitations, these categories are presented in aggregated form and are not further disaggregated by subcategory.

Top 5 by EGSS employment share in 2022

Gross Value Added in the EGSS in the EU-27

in € Mio. and as a percentage of GDP

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National expenditure on environmental protection in 2022

Percentage of GDP

Environmental tax revenues in the EU-27

in € Mio. measured at current prices

Subsidies to environmental harmful practices proxied by total energy subsidies in the EU-27 in € bn. expressed in 2023 constant prices and percentages of GDP

Energy subsidies by environmental impact in the EU-27

in € bn. expressed in 2023 constant prices

Energy subsidies are environmentally harmful if the price or cost reduction that they bring about maintains or increases the availability or the use of energy sources that cause significant negative environmental impacts.

There are subsidies that are categorized as “fossil fuel subsidy” and “not environmentally harmful” – typically these are linked to measures such as covering the cost of closing coal power plants, to rehabilitating former mine sites or to social measures.

Total Green Investments

Percentages by category

Climate Action Network (CAN) Europe's calculations show that for the 2021-27 period, **130.7 billion Euros** have been allocated to the **green transition** across the 27 EU member states' cohesion policy **spending plans**.

These figures include the contributions of **cohesion policy funds** to **climate mitigation**, **biodiversity protection and restoration**, and **circular economy** targets – excluding climate adaptation investments. For a more complete picture, further data is needed to illustrate where private-sector spending is being directed across member states across the same timeframe.

Observations:

- Biodiversity is increasingly on the agenda of European countries, with a few countries taking it as seriously as energy-related investments in terms of public funding priorities
- In 2024, about 47% of the EU's net electricity generation came from renewable sources (including wind, solar, hydro, biomass, etc.) and across the EU's whole energy system, renewables make up about a quarter (~25%) of energy consumption
- Cleaner energy investments are known to have beneficial impact on nature, in terms of lower SO₂, NO_x, and particulate matter, as well as reduced mining, acid rain and damage to forests, crops, and freshwater ecosystems.
- However, nature-negative aspects of non-biodiversity categories need to be **managed carefully**, considering land-use, spatial planning and avoiding overreliance on i.e., forest biomass, large hydropower, rare earth minerals, etc.

Landscape of relevant Policy Instruments

Europe has a range of current laws, strategies and frameworks, whereby markets, businesses and governments are expected to operate within environmental limits, making it a global leader versus other economies. How do we judge their effectiveness and which policy levers need to be strengthened?

Key Progress Highlights

Policy and economic environment

Global targets for nature loss have failed and will not be achieved by 2030 (WWF Living Planet Report, 2024)

Current targets have failed and transformative change is required to reach them by 2030 and beyond, with 30% of them stalled or getting worse from the 2015 baseline. National biodiversity strategies and action plans lack financial and institutional support. Biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation are estimated at almost US\$7 trillion per year, and in contrast Nature based Solutions funding is c. \$200bn. Over half of GDP is moderately or highly dependent on nature and its services. Notable food production is the leading cause of habitat loss, accounts for 70% of water use and is responsible for over a quarter of greenhouse gas emissions.

81% of habitats are in poor status in the EU (European Commission, 2021)

Soil degradation resulting in EUR50bn per year in the EU. Agri output of 5bn is dependent on pollinators which is at risk. Around 25% of global disease burden is attributed to avoidable environmental factors. Also, 1 in 3 bee and butterfly species are in decline. The European Nature Restoration Regulation will set legally binding targets nature restoration across habitats in an attempt to address the challenges.

Key Progress Highlights

Policy and economic environment

EU Omnibus proposals for corporate sustainability reporting (CSRD , CSDDD, Taxonomy) (EC, 2024)

According to European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS), biodiversity is a core mandatory topic and will mandate that the largest firms (under 15,000 enterprises) identify and disclose main pressures and impacts on biodiversity, key sites where operations may affect biodiversity, dependencies on natural inputs and systems, as well as physical and transition risks and opportunities. This is encouraging enterprise take-up of frameworks such as TNFD, BGF Target 15 and SBTN. However, most of Europe's economy is made up of SMEs who are not included. The emerging Omnibus II proposal may support investment but is fueling deregulation concerns.

EU Biodiversity Strategy Dashboard - out of 29, progress is being made for 10 sub-targets (EC, 2025)

Based on current tracking, half of the actions under the strategy's four pillars – protecting areas, restoring ecosystems, enabling transformative change, and external action and now completed. Sadly, common bird and pollinator populations continue to decline, resulting in negative trends for two sub-targets. The pace of designated new protected areas and transition to organic farming needs to triple to get back on-track.

Key Progress Highlights

Fiscal and business environment

Nature-negative financial flows and subsidies (Bloomberg, 2024; UNEP, 2022)

The investment gap for nature is widening: \$948bn nature investment gap in Oct 2024 from \$700bn in 2020. Activities with a direct negative impact on nature is estimated around \$7 trillion (\$1.7tn - public funding and \$5tn - private funding), with the public sector investing the most (80%) in nature-positive financial flows (\$165bn).

Macro-criticality of nature-related risks for the financial system and the economy (European Central Bank, 2025)

Around 72% of Euro area firms are critically dependent on ecosystem services, and these firms account for $\frac{3}{4}$ of all corporate bank lending in the region, representing a future threat for financial stability. Water-related risks are dominant and could constitute 7 - 9% of global GDP, with significant impacts on the manufacturing sector.

Not enough nature targets and transition plans (McKinsey, 2022; WBA 2024)

McKinsey found 83% of the world's top 500 firms have set climate-related targets, although 51% of them acknowledge biodiversity loss, only 5% have set biodiversity targets. Similarly, WBA found only 5% of c. 800 firms have assessed impact on nature and less than 1% assessed dependencies on nature.

Key Progress Highlights

Fiscal and business environment

Assessment of biodiversity impact for Financial Institutions (Finance for Biodiversity, 2025)

200 financial institutions, representing €23 trillion in assets, have committed to assess their impacts on biodiversity, set targets to reduce them, and engage with their investees to increase positive impacts on nature.

Strong but untapped Retail Investor demand (Sustainable Finance Observatory, 2025)

Around 74% of EU retail investors have sustainability-related objectives. However, in most client advisory meetings, sustainability preferences are not assessed and only 19% of investors hold sustainable financial products. Therefore, private EU household savings for NP investments are an untapped opportunity.

Increased reporting of exposure (ICAEW, 2024)

Nature risks are partly covered under environmental pillar of ESG (USD 53+ tr in assets) but TNFD seeks to go beyond this framing, with 500 organizations voluntarily committed to public reporting against TNFD criteria, representing USD 6.5+ tr in market capitalization (publicly listed) and USD 17.5 trillion (assets under management).

Reducing risks and increasing resilience

Europe's economy is currently heavily dependent on nature and at risk of systemic shocks from nature degradation. Europe also has a significant dependency on imports of natural resources and highly complex value chains and global trade flows.

1. The [ECB \(2024\)](#) highlights that many ecosystem services are “public goods” and under-valued or unpriced, meaning nature degradation introduces real economic fragility. They also estimate global habitat loss linked to European economic activity, with euro-area non-financial corporations causing around 217 million hectares of natural habitat loss outside Europe. Also, 75% of euro-area bank loans go to companies that have a high exposure to nature risks.
2. Furthermore, the [ECB \(2024\)](#) (drawing on the INCA project) estimated the value of ecosystem services in the EU (2019) at €234 billion/year. Examples include: nature recreation (~€80.3bn), water purification (~€61.9bn), flood control (~€18bn), carbon sequestration (~€13.3bn), and pollination (~€4.9bn).
3. An ENEA-MA (2013) report points out that the costs associated with the Natura 2000 network (conservation and restoration programme) is estimated at €5.8 bn/year — meaning the economic and social benefits (c.200–300 bn) far outweigh the management cost in their assessments. Similarly, EC (2025) based on data underpinning the Nature Restoration Regulation, every 1 Euro invested into nature restoration adds €4 to €38 in benefits.

Increasing nature and linkages to prosperity and well-being

Relative to value of natural capital, Europe needs to invest more to pivot its current scientific, industrial and entrepreneurial base towards transformative solutions that address long-term environmental concerns, tapping into increasing societal acceptance for products and services that benefit nature.

1. A [JRC](#) (2021) report estimated “selected seven ecosystem services” generated ~€172 bn/year in the EU. Another [JRC](#) (2025) study shows that natural capital contributes significantly to regional economic growth. Specifically: a 10% increase in natural capital (in their model) is associated with a 0.7% rise in regional Gross Value Added (GVA)
2. From the recent NetworkNature / EU [expert report](#): the transition to a nature-positive economy could unlock up to USD 10 trillion of business potential annually (globally) and nearly 400 million jobs by 2030 (EC, 2025).
3. A Naturvation (2020) study estimating the economic value of nature-based solutions (green infrastructure, urban green spaces) in European cities finds USD 1.52 billion/year of value from recent NBS.
4. The [EIC](#) has announced €50 million in funding to develop solutions for climate, which includes nature-based solutions. EU [LIFE](#) funding has allocated €2.15 billion of funding for nature and biodiversity. In the [Horizon Europe](#) programme, between 2021-2027, there is a budget of c.€8.952 billion for NbS.

Summary of Key Findings 1

Europe has strong policy ambitions and a growing green economy, but nature-positive investment remains insufficient, misaligned, and largely led by public funding.

Nature loss is creating systemic economic and financial risks, while the value of ecosystem services and restoration benefits is vastly underpriced. Closing the finance, implementation, and data gaps are critical to unlocking a resilient, nature-positive economy in Europe.

1. Europe is building jobs around nature, but is there more that can be done around building high-value and resilient nature-positive industries at scale?
2. To what extent do other environmental sectors (i.e., clean tech) count towards nature-positive, particularly in terms of mitigation and why might direct investment in biodiversity be better for some European countries?
3. Governments are simultaneously paying to restore nature and paying to degrade it and public budgets may be working against themselves.
4. Europe has a measurable nature-positive economic base, but financial flows are misaligned, and nature-positive activity is still overshadowed by nature-negative incentives.
5. Europe taxes environmental harm, but it is unclear if this is effectively converted into revenue to support nature recovery.
6. Globally, Europe leads on policy design, but transformational delivery, financing, and scale appear to be critical weaknesses.
7. Nature loss is a systemic financial risk, yet business and finance responses remain early-stage and insufficient.
8. Nature is not just an environmental issue — it is a core economic asset, and investing in it yields high social and economic returns and value.
9. Nature risk appears to be recognized at macro level but less so at firm level.

Nature-positive economy roadmaps

*What can we learn from existing
roadmaps and market opportunities?*

KEY FINDINGS 2 – Mapping existing NPE Roadmaps

NPE Roadmaps

The following roadmaps in this section were carefully selected based on their scope, ambition and specific actionable recommendations that have the potential to address nature-negative and/or increase nature-positive outcomes, as opposed to broad frameworks.

The analysis of roadmap data looks at:

- 1) Comparison of future visions
- 2) Comparison of future visions mapped alongside thematic areas of most promising market opportunities
- 3) Comparison of pathways to transformation

We welcome suggestions to review other compelling NPE roadmaps, ideally cross-sector, perhaps at city level and in other languages. However project resources are limited, preventing an exhaustive approach.

LIST OF SOURCES:

1. Biodiversitäts-Strategie Österreich 2030+ (Austria)
2. Transition Strategies toward Nature Positive Economy (Japan)
3. Nature Positive Plan: better for the Environment, better for Business (Australia)
4. Recovering Nature for Growth, Health and Security: Natural England's Strategy (England)
5. Nature Credits Roadmap (European Commission)
6. Global Roadmap for a Nature-Positive Economy (WWF)
7. Exponential Roadmap for Natural Climate Solutions (Exponential Roadmap Initiative)
8. Roadmaps to Nature Positive: Foundations for all Businesses (WBCSD)
9. Vision 2050 (WBCSD)
10. Business Investment in Nature (UK)

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Comparison of future visions across selected nature-positive economy roadmaps

Each documented vision is color coded to a corresponding roadmap (bottom of page) and is positioned against a timeline (top of page) and a cluster (grey, boxes).

Our analysis led us to map visions across six prominent clusters. Some may also have relevance across two or more clusters.

Our 10 areas of promising market opportunities (in purple), are based on a review of existing literature and mapped to a corresponding cluster.

	2025-2029		2030-2049				2050 +				
AMBITION ENVIRONMENTAL AND BIODIVERSITY POLICY GOALS	Recovering nature: increase scale and quality of places where nature thrives	End illegal deforestation by 2025 and end 80% of commodity supply chains with major forest risks Place 40% of agricultural soil under sustainable management by 2028 and increase to 60% by 2030	Effectively protect valuable ecosystems within protected areas and enhance ecological connectivity *Deliver 30x30 targets (30% land and sea protected by 2030)	Governance of the global commons Reduce pollutants entering the water environment through sustainable drainage and wetlands Between now and 2030, companies will mobilize resources for nature impact mitigation and nature restoration across key value chains to implement the GBF and accompanying policy measures	Trade and investment rules Collaboration and dialogues on international trade and investment By 2030, companies have come together to define and take action to halt and reverse nature loss across key systems, bridging the divide between nature action and investment to radically accelerate investment in solutions	Restored 15m ht peatlands (2030) and 250m ht forests and wetlands Grand designs for the conservation, restoration, and rehabilitation of nature in land use	Protect 30% of global terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems by 2030 Restore 75% of water bodies to good ecological status Implement woodland creation to slow water flow	Halve the cost of restoration by 2030 and increased seed and nursery capacity \$300bn of harmful agricultural and forestry subsidies are redirected to regenerative production models by 2030	Reduce land use and fragmentation Improve the status and trends of species and habitats	By 2050, 50% of population globally switch to sustainable diets By 2050, livestock no longer eat crops for humans	ENVIRONMENTAL FM&C SYSTEMS CHANGE Economy working within planetary limits, national transition plans, negative subsidies
STRATEGIC BUSINESS TRANSFORMATION GOALS	Individual company action: By 2025, WBCSD's member companies are advancing on their nature journey from a 2021 readiness baseline	Building better places: greener homes and infrastructure Sector Transition Pathways	Establish ambitious strategies, investments and transition plans aligned with nature positive across value chains	Better alignment with 2030, companies will mobilize resources for nature impact mitigation and nature restoration across key value chains to implement the GBF and accompanying policy measures	Integrate biodiversity considerations ("mainstreaming") across all societal sectors and the economy	NPE ENVIRONMENTAL TECHNOLOGIES Scale uptake of digital systems (i.e. sensors, analytics, apps)	Reduce nitrogen, phosphorus and sediment pollution from agriculture by at least 40% by 2038	Reduce extended producer responsibility Eliminate avoidable waste	Drive extended producer responsibility Eliminate avoidable waste	Double resource productivity by 2050 Cut water company leakage by 50% by 2050	NP AND CIRCULAR BUSINESS PRACTICES Mainstream biodiversity and NCA tools and metrics, risks and opportunities, footprinting, regen business models, etc.
ALIGNED AND TRANSFORMATIVE CLIMATE, NATURE AND SOCIETAL GOALS	Improving health and wellbeing: building nature into everyday life, wherever they live	Delivering security through nature: helping society adapt to climate, resilient food production, healthy soils, clean air, water	Restore ecosystems of high relevance for biodiversity and climate protection Mechanisms for sustainable trade	Better alignment with 2030, companies will mobilize resources for nature impact mitigation and nature restoration across key value chains to implement the GBF and accompanying policy measures	Climate-smart mgt. adopted by agriculture (20%) and timber producing forests (65%) by 2030	Halve emissions by 2030 from natural ecosystems loss	ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION REDUCTION Reduce plastics, reduce tonnage and toxicity of chemicals, reduce reliance on fossil fuel fertilisers	Reduce the use of public water supply in England per head by 20%	Reduce the use of public water supply in England per head by 20%	Agricultural output doubled by improved land and water productivity Sustainability embedded in all products and lifestyles CO2 emissions reduced by 50% worldwide (based on 2025 levels) Near universal access to reliable and low carbon mobility, infrastructure & information	
APPLIED PRACTICAL STANDARDS, INDICATORS AND ASSESSMENTS	Systematically approach the understanding of nature related dependencies and impact, risks and opportunities (DIRO)		Simplify complicated and outdated assessment process	Deliver public dashboards and environmental-economic accounts	NPE Taxonomies	Data collection and information sharing	Global Standards and alt indicators for national accounting	Establish National Standards for NP Outcomes	NPE KNOWLEDGE SERVICES Nature data, standardised KPIs and metrics, SBTN, corporate transparency, benchmarking, landscape-scale initiatives, science policy-practice networks		
MOBILIZED FINANCE AND INVESTMENT FOR NATURE	Accelerate the implementation of nature target setting, financial risk assessments and nature-related disclosures	Create a market framework to allow private investment in biodiversity restoration	Utilization of natural capital in various national and local government projects, etc.	Economic instruments such as credits, offsets etc. related to natural capital and biodiversity	Financial regulatory frameworks and collaboration for enabling policy environment	Global insurance mechanisms and collaboration for nature-related risks	Align with carbon markets and enable offset-based conservation payments	NATURE MARKETS Scale mandatory BNG, credits, payment for ecosystem services and stewardship			
	Mobilise investor confidence by defining quality criteria, safeguards, and risk mitigation	Create robust governance to avoid greenwashing	Establish Clear EU standards and a reliable certification system for a voluntary nature credits market	Debt relief and restructuring	Innovative financing mechanisms	NPE FINANCIAL AND LEGAL SERVICES Mobilizing sector, embedding NP, mainstreaming NP across financial products, capacity building, etc.	Invest £100m to improve coastal and flood defences in the most exposed areas				
STRONGER NATURE PROTECTION MEASURES AND CONSERVATION EFFORTS	By 2025, establish an independent Environmental Protection Agency	Complete first round of regional planning by 2028	Develop regional plans using 3 zone "traffic lights" (protected, managed, low constraint)	Strengthen global dimensions of biodiversity conservation	Recognise 2bn hectares of IPLC land	NP investment, development strategies and capacity building in developing countries	NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS Scale up in high impact sectors, as well as for climate adaptation and disaster risk reduction	Develop engagement standards and integrate Indigenous knowledge into planning and conservation	Four to tenfold improvement in the eco-efficiency of resources & materials from 2000		

Existing NPE Roadmaps ->

- Biodiversitäts-Strategie Österreich 2030+ (Austria)
- Transition Strategies toward Nature Positive Economy (Japan)
- Nature Positive Plan: better for the Environment, better for Business (Australia)
- Recovering Nature for Growth, Health and Security: Natural England's Strategy
- Nature Credit's Roadmap (European Commission)
- Global Roadmap for a Nature-Positive Economy (WWF)
- Exponential Roadmap for Natural Climate Solutions (Exponential Roadmap Initiative)
- Roadmaps to Nature Positive: Foundations for all Businesses (WBCSD)
- Vision 2050 (WBCSD)
- Business Investment in Nature (UK)

Comparison of pathways to transformation across selected nature-positive economy roadmaps

PATHWAYS		2025-2030									
POLICY DRIVERS	Natural Resources	Targeted protected site strategies, addressing water, air, soil challenges and climate change impacts	Expand NBS to reduce flood risk, improve water quality, address water scarcity and defend against extreme heat	Improve soils, water, air and reduce chemicals impacting nature, through farming advice and agri-environment funding schemes	Pathways to nature recovery for National Parks and Landscapes	Growing National Nature Reserve Network and designation of super NRR	Better utilisation and productivity of natural resources				
	Planning and Infrastructure	Work with local councils, gov, business to increase NP offer and uptake of NP tools for home building and infrastructure	Gov department works with infrastructure developers plan NP into early design and planning	Setting standards for urban green infrastructure and offering incentive of accreditation to a national programme	National biodiversity strategy and development of new metrics	Climate-critical protected areas	Forest and wetland restoration				
	Public Sector Services	Increasing provision of high quality inclusive nature access for all, using national trails	Embed access and engagement with nature into public sector statutory and advice work	Targeted support to healthcare education and employment sectors, to bring nature into plans	Support to local spatial planning and place-based strategies to embed nature	Green social prescribing integrated into public health policy and plans	Public education, encouraging citizen action and participation	Dietary shift and food waste	Decision-support		
	Working with Industry	Local nature recovery strategies are linked to regional growth priorities	Deliver strategic schemes to maximise nature recovery at scale	Reward NP early adopters and maintain and improve international competitiveness	Encourage clean energy low carbon providers to increase nature across land and sea	Support creation of new industries	Partner to increase gov-approved nature markets projects				
	Public Funding	Funding recovery projects and partnerships that reduce the risk of extinction to the most threatened species	Restoration funding: repairing ecosystems, community groups, science funding to inform decision-making	Dedicated biodiversity fund and increased support for restoration projects	Implement joint-pilot projects 2025-2027, focusing on small producers and SMEs	Piloting carbon removal practices with biodiversity benefits (co-benefits)	Align corporate plans with national nature goals				

Each NPE roadmap provides an indication of initiatives and activities over the next five years (2025-2030) that must be pursued to achieve their respective visions.

These can also be clustered as drivers of change, some of which cut across stakeholder groups or require collaboration between them to achieve the desired outcomes. Each driver can be further grouped (i.e., natural resources) based on related goals.

PRIVATE SECTOR DRIVERS	Leadership and Strategy	Business leadership and advocacy for NP business models, supporting systemic change and long-term outcomes	Increase in companies setting science-informed target setting (i.e. SBTN) for avoidance and NP, integrated into business operations metrics	Increase in individual business transformation strategies, based on Dependencies, Impacts, Risks and Opportunities (DIROs) findings	Align business strategy with nature finance and deploy (capex, opex) into NP projects	Large enterprises to integrate nature into business functions, going beyond a siloed environment team	Mainstreaming	NP transition pathways
	Risks and Benefits	Companies adopt ACT-D Framework (Assess, Commit, Transform, Disclose)	Value-chain materiality screening for nature impacts and dependencies	Detailed assessments and commonly agreed indicators for nature disclosures	Promote management of hazardous substances that damage nature by preventing their leakage or use of alternatives	Support sustainable technologies and business models that reduce nature harm	No-deforestation supply chains	Foster cross-sector collaboration across supply chains
SCIENCE, DATA AND KNOWLEDGE DRIVERS	Standards and Reporting	Strengthen science, monitoring and knowledge and creation of public database of projects and biodiversity dashboard	National environment information: publish "state of the environment" every two years, increasing transparency	Strong EU methods and governance for robust monitoring, verification and transparency – avoiding continuity of nature harms (via offsetting)	Certification system for NP Actions, measuring activity and outcomes but with reduced admin burden	Setting standards for NP recovery on publicly owned land and work across sectors with landowners	Set standards and frameworks that give confidence for green investments	
	Evidence and Data	Address lack of quantitative data and metrics to report on progress on each step of 'Assess' and 'Commit and Transform'	Matching and information dissemination to promote the use of technologies supporting NP	Work towards national environmental standards, with new offset hierarchy and net gain requirements	Climate smart farming	Basic science	Trials and evidence	Enhance analysis of nature-related risks and opportunities
FINANCE SECTOR DRIVERS	Increasing Investment	Hosting Global Nature Positive Summit to catalyse private sector investment and scale-up restoration projects	Budget investment to stated reforms and build capacity in the Nature Repair Market	Increase blended finance (via credits) with EU funds and encourage regions/cities to set up nature e credit funds and bottom up initiatives	International financial institutions and development financing institutions	Shifting private capital		
	Governance	Self-service regulation, supported by advice, training and compliance framework for developers, to reduce time and costs	Pilot projects of models of nature credit markets via Green Assist (EC Experts Network) and a supply and demand assessment	Expert group to develop standards and governance for nature credits (EU level)	Additional requirements for NP in the adoption of subsidies and grants for NP projects	Business investment in nature restoration		
SOCIETAL DRIVERS	Cultural Change	Foster societal culture that values biodiversity and drive change through public institutions – i.e. start with public procurement and organic food	Utilising culture and local, traditional knowledge		IPCL rights and resources	Requires community involvement to ensure legitimacy and equitable benefit-sharing		
	Science Policy Gap	Increase bioscience controls – monitoring, warning systems, public engagement	Adopt ecosystem-based management to secure healthy seas, benefitting coastal communities	Biodiversity and species protection with new cultural heritage protections, bioscience measures and threatened species action plan (10 year)	Global engagement – assess national consumption and economic impacts beyond Europe and encourage biodiversity friendly consumption	Use of nature-based solutions addressing environmental values of resource recycling, disaster prevention and mitigation, revitalisation of local economies, water and air quality conservation, maximising synergies with social values such as health, etc.	Regional and financial sectors: Measures to make NP initiatives a solution to issues and business opportunities in the region	Consider rights and payments for stewards of nature
	Nature society business Nexus	Land managers and local communities are successfully claiming new income for NP interventions	Develop more explicit guidance on how to work with equality and justice					IMF and WTO consider IP&LC rights and IPR in trade decision-making

Existing NPE Roadmaps ->	Biodiversitäts-Strategie Österreich 2030+ (Austria)	Transition Strategies toward Nature Positive Economy (Japan)	Nature Positive Plan: better for the Environment, better for Business (Australia)	Recovering Nature for Growth, Health and Security: Natural England's Strategy	Nature Credits Roadmap (European Commission)	Global Roadmap for a Nature-Positive Economy (WWEF)	Exponential Roadmap for Natural Climate Solutions (Exponential Roadmap Initiative)	Roadmaps to Nature Positive: Foundations for all Businesses (WBCSD)	Business Investment in Nature (UK)	No Pathways in Vision 2050 (WBCSD)
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Summary of Key Findings 2 and Recommendations for Future Work

Taking a system wide view and comparison of pioneering NPE roadmaps allows us to take stock and visually absorb a variety of emerging future visions, market opportunities and transformation pathways. In the next stage our work, we will look at transformation across:

- 1) Policy level changes at national level
- 2) Rules of the game changes at international level
- 3) Guidance or agreed frameworks at corporate level
- 4) Specific solutions at instrument/practice level

Roadmap components in each vision and pathway are not necessarily in competition. They provide direction at various scales over time and offer potential for a more in-depth analysis within each cluster. This may uncover impactful opportunities for synergy and to maximise the rate of return on natural capital investment across Europe. In each area, our work raises key questions such as 'what are the gaps and key enablers' and 'what are the key roadblocks' over the next five years and beyond.

CONSULTATION

We invite experts from business, government, finance, research, standards, citizens groups and nature-based enterprises to provide feedback on the content of this document – feedback to dharm.kapletia@tcd.ie.

NEXT STEPS

- 1) Further analyse the linkages between the baseline situation in Europe and how future visions and pathways will specifically address current challenges
- 2) Map which 'pathways to transformation' will accelerate the performance of current and planned European policies and regulations (aligned to the NPE)
- 3) Combine this high-level analysis with an aggregate analysis of the project's six pilot (sectoral) roadmaps to draw more robust conclusions (integrating top-down and bottom-up)
- 4) Combine all insights and work towards the delivery of a high-level GoNaturePositive! NPE Roadmap, for release in 2027

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